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EVALUATION OF FILLERS IN GRAY BOARD PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

In this study, usage of fillers during gray board production was investigated and it was aimed to reduce production cost by using waste office, magazine, newspaper, and writing-printing papers and fillers as raw materials in gray board production. In addition, usability of ECC (eggshell calcium carbonate) and PCC (precipitated calcium carbonate) which has never been used and commonly used GCC (ground calcium carbonate) filler in gray board production have been investigated. As a result, breaking length (3.30 km), burst index (2.27 kPa.m²/g), tear index (6.53 mN.m²/g), Cobb (298 g/m²) and surface roughness (21.3 µm) of gray boards produced with using ECC were higher than those of gray board produced with using PCC and GCC. Whiteness (55.1 ISO%), brightness (51.2 ISO%) and yellowness (10.5 E313) of the gray board (ECC) found to be similar to the optical properties of PCC and GCC added gray boards. As a result of this study, the use of fillers in gray board production both reduces the cost and improves the optical properties.

Keywords: ECC, GCC, Gray board, PCC, waste paper.

1. INTRODUCTION

More than one industrial product is used as raw material in paper production. These industrial products are used for two different purposes as coating and fillers materials (Eroglu & Usta, 2004). The use of fillers in paper production improves opacity, size, whiteness, print quality and ink absorption. Paper producers have begun to use calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) as filler mineral to improve these paper properties (Gill, 1995; Han & Seo, 1997; Koivunen & Paulapuro, 2010). However, the number of fiber-to-fiber bonds decreases with the addition of fillers, resulting in reductions in paper strengths. Therefore, paper producers should determine the filler ratio during paper production without decreasing the strength properties too much (Haller et al., 2001).

Gray board is produced from waste papers such as recycled printing, office, magazine and newspaper. It can be produced depending on usage area between 140 (g/m²) and 400 (g/m²) grammages. Gray boards and cardboards materials can be used in many sectors such as bobbin, core board, bracket, textile, egg carton, candy boxes, notebook covers and shoeboxes. A very small amount of fillers (GCC) is used in the production of gray cardboard in the world. In particular, the use of fillers is important in gray board production used in printing processes. As mentioned previously, the fillers improve the optical and printing properties (Cesur, 2018).

Calcium carbonate content increased with increasing paper production in alkaline condition. Ground calcium carbonate (GCC) is commonly used as filler in paper production. However, almost all of the GCC usage takes place in white papers production. In 1972, GCC was used as a filler in the manufacture of coating and special papers. Initially, the GCC was replaced by coating formulations in precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC), but successful results were obtained in North America with using PCC. Thus, the use of PCC has again become advantageous and it was the third largest filler after GCC and kaolin. Calcium carbonate obtained by grinding eggshells (ECC) is of great importance in terms of cost (Erkan & Malayoglu, 2001). The contribution of PCC as a filler in paper production to the brightness and opacity of paper is greater than that of all other fillers. Because PCC has excellent light scattering capability and inherent whiteness, brightness and chemical purity. The better shape and filling of the void volumes formed in the paper matrix also increase the internal light scattering of the paper (Tutus et al., 2012).

Fillers are mainly used in the paper industry for two main reasons: to make the production system more economical and to make changes in the technical properties of the paper material to be produced (Karademir et al., 2013). The use of fillers in the production of paper from particularly expensive bleached fibers has become very important in terms of economy. The use of fillers is also expected to increase due to recent increases in pulp prices. The use of fillers in waste paper recycling enterprises is quite low. However, increases in waste paper prices may push them to use fillers. In a study, fillers were used in paper production from waste papers, PCC and GCC were compared and it was found that the papers produced with using PCC had better optical

and physical properties (Tutus et al., 2013). Due to the decrease in the number of fiber-fiber bonds, the physical properties of the papers decreased but the optical properties improved.

In this study, it was aimed to investigate effects of using different fillers in gray board production on physical and optical properties. As fillers, commonly used GCC, PCC obtained by chemical precipitation and ECC obtained by grinding eggshells were used.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Waste eggshells supplied from patisseries, ground calcium carbonate (GCC) and precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) taken from Adaçal Industrial Minerals Inc. were used as filler. The waste eggshells were cleaned and ground, sieved in a 200 mesh sieve and calcium carbonates passed under the sieve were used as filler (ECC).

In this study, waste office papers (60%) and waste gray boards (40%) were recycled and beaten by using Hollander device. As a result of ash analysis, the presence of 10% filler in the recycled pulp was determined. Then, PCC, GCC and ECC fillers were added to pulp at the ratios specified in Table 1 below and gray boards were produced.

Table 1. Mixing ratios of recycled pulps and fillers used in gray board production

Recycled pulp (%)	PCC (%)	GCC (%)	ECC (%)
100	0	0	0
95	5	-	-
90	10	-	-
85	15	-	-
80	20	-	-
95	-	5	-
90	-	10	-
85	-	15	-
80	-	20	-
95	-	-	5
90	-	-	10
85	-	-	15
80	-	-	20

Ten gray boards with 320 ± 3 (g.m^{-2}) grammages were manufactured using a Rapid Kothen sheet former according to ISO 5269-2:2004. The gray boards were calendered for 3 seconds under 170°C and 25 bar pressure. All tests of the produced boards were carried out according to ISO, ASTM and TAPPI test methods and the gray boards were subjected to the tests specified in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Optical, physical tests and standards applied to gray boards

Physical and Optical Tests	Standards
Breaking length	TAPPI T494 om-01
Burst index	TAPPI T403 om-15
Surface roughness	ISO 4287
Cobb ₆₀	TAPPI T 835 om-94
Brightness	ISO 2469:2014
Whiteness	ISO 2469:2014
Yellowness	ASTM E313

SPSS was used to determine the effect on the physical and optical properties of gray boards produced by adding PCC, GCC and ECC fillers. Test results were determined by one-way analysis of variance and Duncan's test for 95% confidence interval ($P < 0.05$). Duncan's test was applied in case of differences between the groups by statistical analysis of variance.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3 indicates the physical and optical properties of gray boards produced adding PCC, GCC and ECC fillers, respectively. According to the table, the physical properties were adversely affected by the addition of filler and using fillers improved the optical properties. When the fibers interact with the fillers, the number of fiber-fiber bonds decreases, thus reducing the physical properties of the cartons (Eroglu & Usta, 2004; Karademir et al., 2013). Since the optical properties of the fillers used in this study are higher than the recycled pulp, the optical properties of the gray boards were found to be better.

Table 3. The physical and optical properties of the gray board produced with adding PCC, GCC and ECC

Filler (%)	Breaking Length (km)	Burst Index (kPa.m ² /g)	Cobb ₆₀ (g.m ⁻²)	Surface Roughness (μm)	Whiteness (ISO%)	Brightness (ISO%)	Yellowness (E313)
PCC							
0	2.735	1.83	358	21.00	53.82	50.77	10.04
5	2.584	1.77	328	17.38	56.18	52.65	10.01
10	2.322	1.34	345	18.37	57.83	55.21	8.14
15	2.260	1.46	308	18.82	59.12	56.05	8.24
20	2.193	1.21	269	19.21	63.45	61.99	4.67
GCC							
0	2.735	1.83	358	21.00	53.82	50.77	10.04
5	2.783	1.73	324	17.88	55.44	52.69	8.69
10	2.743	1.62	303	17.99	57.40	54.90	7.66
15	2.614	1.54	278	18.11	59.54	56.18	8.54
20	2.224	1.32	268	18.57	61.36	58.61	7.55
ECC							
0	2.735	1.83	358	21.00	53.82	50.77	10.04
5	3.297	2.27	298	21.25	52.13	48.58	11.04
10	3.205	1.82	305	22.21	53.49	49.97	10.63
15	2.462	1.29	351	23.66	54.64	50.90	10.51
20	2.189	1.25	338	25.67	55.05	51.52	10.45

As the PCC and GCC fillers ratios increased in the gray boards, it was observed that the breaking lengths and burst indices of the gray boards decreased. The desired values according to the standard determined by Kahramanmaraş Paper Inc. is 2.10 km and 1.01 kPa.m².g⁻¹ (Anonymous, 2018). When the results were examined, it was found that obtained values were above the standard values. Therefore, it is suitable to use up to 25% PCC and GCC as filler in gray board production in terms of physical properties. The surface roughness values were improved by addition of PCC and GCC. Improvements were observed when compared to the control gray board surface roughness. The water absorbency (Cobb) of the gray boards have been reduced by addition PCC and GCC. Fillers penetrated between the hydrophilic fibers and reduced their water absorption ability. PCC and GCC improve the surface smoothness and print quality of the paper and boards. Besides, calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), which is an alkali filler in particular, reduces the aging of paper and boards by preventing significant degradation due to acid hydrolysis in cellulose fibers (Karademir et al., 2013).

In Figure 1 below, the effects of the 20% fillers addition on the physical and optical properties in the gray board production were given.

Figure 1. Comparison of effects of fillers on some physical and optical properties

Figure 1 also indicates the comparison of the effects of fillers on the physical and optical properties of gray boards. It was observed that the use of filler improves the optical properties of gray boards and decreases the physical properties. The highest value in optical properties was obtained by using PCC, while the lowest value was obtained by adding ECC. With the use of 20% PCC in gray board production, whiteness and brightness values increased by 17.9% and 22.1%, while yellowness decreased by 53.5%. Addition of GCC in gray board production also enhanced the optical properties such as whiteness, brightness, and yellowness. The use of ECC has not been as effective on the optical properties of gray boards as PCC and GCC. In a study, it is determined that PCC has higher whiteness and brightness than GCC (Muduroglu & Arsoy, 2012). Addition of GCC gave the highest physical properties compared to other fillers. However, it has shown better results in terms of physical properties than other fillers. Even with the use of 5% ECC, the physical properties of gray boards improved. When surface roughness values were compared, PCC and GCC gave surface properties compared to ECC. As the calcium carbonates have higher surface area than cellulose fibers, the surface roughness of the gray boards was reduced (Haller et al., 2001).

4. CONCLUSION

The results of this study, which investigated the evaluation of PCC, GCC and ECC fillers in gray board production and compared the effects of fillers on physical and optical properties, were given as follows;

1. As a result of the use of calcium carbonate based fillers that are not widely used in gray cardboard production, it has been determined that there are no drawbacks in accordance with the standards determined by Kahramanmaraş Paper Inc.
2. PCC and GCC had a significant effect on the optical properties of gray boards, but not ECC. Therefore, the use of PCC and GCC in gray board production would be advantageous where optical properties are important.
3. The use of fillers reduced the physical properties of gray cartons, but the ECC had the least effect. Even the use of 5% ECC had a positive effect on physical properties. Therefore, it is possible to produce gray cardboard with better physical properties by using ECC as filler.
4. The use of fillers not only reduces production costs but also ensures the long-lasting gray cardboard production. Especially with the addition of cheaper ECC in gray board production, costs can be reduced further.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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